

D4.7 Pilot III: Final Report

Author(s): Pierre Baviera,
Swaroop Bhat, Katharine Cooney,
Julia Bosque Gil, Mario Romera

Date: December 2021

H2020-ICT-29b

Grant Agreement No. 825182

Prêt-à-LLOD - Ready-to-use Multilingual
Linked Language Data for Knowledge
Services across Sectors

D4.7 Pilot III: Final Report

Deliverable Number: D28

Dissemination Level: Public

Delivery Date:

Version: 1

Author(s): Pierre Baviera, Swaroop Bhat, Katharine Cooney, Julia Bosque Gil, Mario Romera

Document History

Version Date	Changes	Authors
July 2021	Additions to section 2.3	K. Cooney
December 2021	Modifications to section 2.3.4	K. Cooney
January 2022	Incorporate feedback from review	K. Cooney

Executive Summary	5
1 Pilot Overview	6
1.1 Introduction and Goals	6
1.2 Pilot Schedule	7
1.3 Functional Requirements	8
1.4 Non-Functional Requirements	8
2 Pilot III.A – Chatbot providing access to Government and Health information	9
2.1 Motivation - Proficiency in English	9
2.2 Use Cases	10
2.2.1 Data Sources	10
2.2.2 Current languages of interest	10
2.2.3 Application Benchmarks	11
2.3 Technical Approach	11
2.3.1 Phase I	11
2.3.2 Phase II (Application Version V1.0):	13
2.3.3 Phase III	19
2.3.4 Phase IV (Integration of University of Bielefeld Question generation software)	22
2.4 Application Benchmarks	24
2.4.1 KPI Contributions	27
2.5 Future plans	27
3 Pilot III.B Open Data Dashboard	28
3.1 Motivation	28
3.2 Use cases	28
Use Case 1	29
Use Case 2	29
Use Case 3	29
3.2.1 Data Sources	29
3.2.2 Languages of Interest	29
3.3 Technical Approach	29
3.3.1 Phase 1	30
3.3.2 Phase 2	31
3.3.3 Phase 3	32
3.3.4 Phase 4	33

3.3.5 Phase 5	34
3.4 Application Benchmarks	34
3.4.1 Testing of Phase 3 (data from data.gov.ie)	34
3.4.2 Testing of Phase 4 (European Open Data Portal)	40
3.4.3 KPI Contributions	42
3.5 Future plans	43
4 Conclusions	43
Appendices	44
Appendix 1 : questions for chatbot	44

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the second version of Derilinx' report on its pilot for Prêt-à-LLOD, developing and reporting Derilinx' achievements from version 1 of the report which was delivered in month 24.

The goal of this pilot is to deliver a Public Service Query Tool providing the following functionality:

1. Answer multilingual queries on Government and Health Services via a Chatbot
2. Explore Open Data via a dashboard

Updates to version 1 of the deliverable have been made in the following sections:

2 Pilot II.A – Chatbot providing access to government and health information

2.3.4 Phase IV (Integration with the University of Bielefeld Question Generation software)

2.4 Application Benchmarks

2.5 Future Plans

3 Pilot II.B Open Data Dashboard

3.1 Motivation

3.2.3 Languages of interest

3.3.4 Phase 4

3.4 Application Benchmarks

4 Summary

1 Pilot Overview

1.1 Introduction and Goals

Derilinx provides services to government for high-quality data publishing and is a leading Linked & Open Data company, driving decision-making and providing insights in the public sector. Derilinx' clients include Government Bodies, Local Authorities and NGOs. Being able to discover, access and use data is key to ensure the effective delivery of public services, to foster trust in the organisations through transparency and to stimulate innovation, both internally and in the wider economy. Derilinx supports its clients in this mission through the publication of high-quality and reusable data.

There is huge potential in the application of Prêt-à-LLOD innovative approaches to language technologies within our existing commercial service offerings, bringing ground-breaking advancements in language technologies to the wider sphere of the government and NGO sectors.

With this pilot, "Supporting the Development of Public Services in Open Government both within and across borders", Derilinx aims to provide tools and interfaces for more intuitive access to open data portals and public services using natural language.

In particular, the goal of this pilot is to explore and use state-of-the-art methods and techniques in computational semantics, data mining and machine learning for linking language data at the level of meaning. It will incorporate Linguistic Linked Open Data (LLOD)/ Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies into our data sharing platform "datAdore"¹, and into Derilinx' wider knowledge management and data-access services. This pilot will free up and connect data that often exists in disparate silos, thus leading to a significant overhead in managing, enriching and reusing this data. In this respect, the work carried out here contributes directly to Challenge 4 of Prêt-à-LLOD, concerning the linking of conceptual and lexical data for language services.

The Pilot specifications distinguish between two parts (or sub-pilots):

Part A Improving the ease of use and the multilingual capability of government and health information services

Access to healthcare and government services can be complicated, even more so for the users trying to access information through a language that is not their own. To facilitate easier access to this information, Artificial Intelligence (AI)/NLP systems can be used to complement other communication channels. Conversational User Interfaces (CUI) such as chatbots can provide more uniform (and multilingual) access to health information and government services and have the potential to optimize citizen interactions. Derilinx is using the pilot to develop a chatbot answering natural language queries regarding public services information that may be in another language. This will provide cross-border and multilingual access to this information.

Part B Improving access to Open Data by facilitating natural language queries and providing multilingual access

Open data portals provide access to data, which is provided in open formats such as CSV, comma delimited files and geoJSON² formats, which are used for data with geolocation information. Although

¹ <https://derilinx.com/datadore/>

² [GeoJSON Specification \(r-project.org\)](https://geojson.org/)

this data is easily machine-readable, it can be more difficult for non-technical users to access, necessitating several steps to find the relevant piece of information inside a file. The open data query tool will allow the user to pose a natural language question in a user interface. The tool will then help identify the relevant file(s), query the contents of these files, and return an answer to the question via a dashboard. This will eventually incorporate the ability to query data that is provided in a different language and return the results in the user’s own language, thus providing cross-border, multilingual access.

The two sub-pilots, consisting of the implementation of a chatbot and an open data dashboard, aim to (1) answer natural language queries regarding public services information via a chatbot and (2) return open data associated with this query, and provide further search functionality via a dashboard. Both the public service information and the open data will be returned in the language of the query, providing a web interface for users to access cross-border government services and open data in their native language.

These pilot tools have been integrated to provide a single interface called “Kweery”.

1.2 Pilot Schedule

It was initially planned to have two separate applications for the two sub-pilots. These have subsequently been merged into a single application and so the development milestones have been changed to reflect this.

Milestone ID	Goal	Due date (Project Month)	Updated Due date (Project Month)
MS-III.1a	High level design agreed	M8	M8
MS-III.2a	Development of test cases for internal (DLX) testing	M10	M10
MS-III.3a	Alpha version of application ready for testing	M12	M12
MS-III.4a	Beta version of application ready for testing	M18	M24
MS-III.5a	Application completes internal testing	M20	M26
MS-III.6a	Pilot user satisfaction survey developed	M21	M26
MS-III.7a	User testing complete	M22	M28
MS-III.8a	Application fully implemented	M24	M30
Milestone ID	Goal	Due date (Project Month)	Updated Due date (Project Month)
MS-III.1b	High level design agreed	M22	M14

MS-III.2b	Development of test cases for internal (DLX) testing	M22	M14
MS-III.3b	Alpha version of application ready for testing	M26	M18
MS-III.4b	Beta version of application ready for testing	M30	M30
MS-III.5b	Application completes internal testing	M32	M32
MS-III.6b	User testing complete	M34	M34
MS-III.7b	Application fully implemented	M36	M36

Figure 1: Pilot milestones

1.3 Functional Requirements

Pilot III.A (Kweery chatbot) focuses in particular on:

- Interpretating and disambiguating natural language questions
- Providing a chatbot in multiple languages

Pilot III.B (Kweery dashboard) focuses in particular on:

- Interpretating and disambiguating natural language queries
- Developing an API that enables interaction between the Kweery Chatbot and the Kweery Dashboard (this API which will work in conjunction with the European data portal³)

1.4 Non-Functional Requirements

The following non-functional requirements are addressed in order to fulfil the proposed functional requirements:

- The Kweery chatbot is extensible (uses APIs) to facilitate the incorporation of Prêt-à-LLOD functionalities as they become available and evolve
- The extension of datAdore (Kweery dashboard) should allow the incorporation of appropriate Prêt-à-LLOD workflows as they become available and evolve
- The chatbot must comply with GDPR and ethical requirements – the chatbot does not store any user information
- The available license agreements should either allow integration of Prêt-à-LLOD components into the chatbot without requiring the chatbot code to be made open source (e.g., Apache or MIT license) or a commercial license needs to be available.

³ <https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets>

2. Pilot III.A – Chatbot providing access to Government and Health information

2.1 Motivation - Proficiency in English

The latest Irish Census (2016) includes in a summary of the top 10 non-Irish nationalities and their own assessment of their ability in English⁴ (Figure 2). Over 58,000 people assess their own ability as “not well, not at all or haven’t stated”. Out of 535,475 non-Irish nationals usually resident in Ireland, this is a significant proportion of whom (103,113) are from the UK and so can be assumed to have ability in English.

Looking at the top 10 non-Irish nationalities alone, this suggests that of non-Irish nationalities, excluding those from the UK, 268,862, there could be some 22% who are significantly disadvantaged by their ability in English and so have limited access to services.

Nationality	Living in Ireland for 2016 Census
Polish	122,515 persons
UK	103,113 persons
Lithuanian	36,552 persons
Romanian	29,186 persons
Latvian	19,933 persons
Brazilian	13,640 persons
Spanish	12,112 persons
Italian	11,732 persons
French	11,661 persons
German	11,531 persons

Figure 2: Top 10 non-Irish nationalities from 2016 Irish Census

Similar analysis for England and Wales⁵ shows a significant proportion (864,000) who say they speak English “not well” or “not well at all”.

As demonstrated above, there is significant potential for providing cross-border multilingual access to health information and government services, particularly for some of the less well-served languages. In fact, Covid-19 has highlighted the importance of reaching the largest possible audience by providing health and government information in multiple languages. In order to identify the languages which would have maximum impact, local census data can be used.

⁴ <https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-cpnin/cpnin/introduction/>
⁵

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/culturalidentity/language/articles/detailedanalysisenglishlanguageproficiencyinenglandandwales/2013-08-30>

2.2 Use Cases

Use cases that we address as part of this pilot are:

Actor	Goal	Extended Goal
General user	Understand how to access the health service in Ireland	I can access and use the health service, for example, how to access hospital services.
General user without the language of the resource	Receive information in my own language on the public services available	I can access and use that public service, for example, understand what Social Welfare benefits, schemes and allowances are available to me.

Figure 3: Use cases for Kweery chatbot

2.2.1 Data Sources

- Irish Citizens' Information Website⁶
- Spanish Travel Information Website⁷

The Kweery chatbot will cover all topics covered by the Irish "Citizens' Information Website". Examples include:

- COVID-19
- Health
- Social Welfare
- Travel and Recreation

It will also cover all topics covered by the Spanish "Information for travelling to Spain" website. This includes:

- Visa and passport
- Security
- Health

2.2.2 Current languages of interest

- Spanish (ES)
- English (EN)
- French (FR)
- German (DE)
- Italian (IT)

⁶ <https://www.citizensinformation.ie/en/>

⁷ <https://www.spain.info/en/info/>

2.2.3 Application Benchmarks

- Quality of response:
 - Analysis of content of application responses against the search provided on the Irish Citizens' Information website, which uses Google Search.
 - Validation of responses in Spanish by a native Spanish speaker
- Planned Beta Testing:
 - User testing with trial users to assess their satisfaction with chatbot responses

2.3 Technical Approach

Kweery Chatbot is implemented using a number of AI technologies, including libraries, formats and approaches coming from NLP , Machine Learning Text Classification, Data Modelling and Information Retrieval.

- NLP: NLTK⁸ (Natural Language Toolkit).
- Machine learning text classification: scikit-learn⁹ (Space Vector Model).
- Data modelling: Comma Delimited file as Knowledge base.
- Information retrieval: TF-IDF¹⁰ (Term frequency-inverse document frequency).

The application stack has been developed over 3 phases. Each phase has been refined from the drawbacks/limitations identified in the previous phase.

2.3.1 Phase I

In this phase Derilinx developed a basic bot which worked on the Information retrieval logic – term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF). All the application logic was developed as one single application.

Figure 4 below shows the application architecture diagram of Phase 1.

⁸ <https://www.nltk.org/>

⁹ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/index.html>

¹⁰ https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978-1-4899-7687-1_832

Figure 4: Kweery chatbot architecture (Phase 1)

Techniques used:

The data was pre-processed using a data pipeline, which takes the raw text and uses standard text cleaning methods, and was then stored in a database. The user-entered query goes through the same data pipeline before the text is analysed.

Information retrieval (TF-IDF) was used to search for relevant text and respond with relevant text. This approach did not show substantial results since a similar text was present in the knowledge base and the semantics of the user query was not successfully captured. Also, calculating TF-IDF score of the entire text in memory resulted in a slow response and limited the scalability of the application.

The application acted as search tool rather than an interactive chatbot. At this stage, the scalability of the application was also limited and we harvested data related to only one domain. These limitations resulted in poor search/response.

Limitations of Phase I:

- Covered data related to only one domain
- Not scalable for different domains
- Multi user not supported
- Poor quality of response
- Not conversational

- No multilingual functionality

A scalable application with increased data volume was planned in Phase II to address these limitations.

2.3.2 Phase II (Application Version V1.0):

This phase aimed to address most of the limitations of Phase I and included a suggestion/recommendation engine, semantic text analysis and text to linked data conversion.

The capability of answering questions in different languages was also added. Currently, the application supports two languages, English (EN) and Spanish (ES).

Figure 5 represents a high level architecture diagram of the application of Phase II and its evolution.

Figure 5: Kweery chatbot architecture (Phase II)

The application is divided into two major components:

- Application programming Interface (API)
- Interactive web app (Dialog framework).

Component 1 - Kweery Application Programming Interface (API)

The APIs are designed as extensions, which allows developers to plugin/remove/update any piece of functionality. In this phase we developed three major extensions - core plugin, NLP plugin and search plugin.

When the data is harvested to the application, it goes through the NLP extension, which handles NLP tasks, and a data cleaning pipeline. This extension extracts semantic meaning from the text and prepares the text for indexing. Information such as named entities, synonyms, hyponyms, hypernyms and text relationships is extracted in this stage.

Below, Figure 6 represents Kweery API software components and how each component is connected to each other.

Figure 6: Kweery chatbot API Architecture

Text Cleaning Pipeline

In this phase, the data pipeline from Phase I was retained. In addition, each text cleaning process was made pluggable, allowing developers to modify or add additional cleaning processes. The core cleaning process includes:

- Extra space removal
- Stemmer (Using NLTK library)
- Lemmatization
- Stop words removal
- Regex pattern extractor
- Domain specific stop words removal

NLP Data Model

For entity extraction the pipeline uses NLTK and SpaCy¹¹ python packages. For detection of synonyms, hypernyms and hyponyms Wordnet¹² is used. This extracted information is then indexed to Elasticsearch¹³ for easy searchability and scalability.

Further information on text relationships is extracted from a combination of SpaCy and NLTK tree parser with custom grammar rules. Information is extracted in the following form:

subject -> predicate -> object.

This relationship extraction step helped in understanding how the components of the text are related to each other and increased search results significantly. In addition, this model can handle huge volumes of the search.

Extracted text relations are then stored in Graph Db (Neo4J¹⁴) for extracting suggestions and recommendations.

Recommendation System

The pipeline uses a graph data model to extract and present the recommendation to the user. That is, for any user entered text, the system extracts text relations and find if the same relations exist. If so, the system extracts all the child and parent components from the stored text and provides these key words as suggestion to the user.

Figure 7 below represents the workflow and components of the recommendation or suggestion system.

¹¹ <https://spacy.io/>

¹² <https://wordnet.princeton.edu/>

¹³ <https://www.elastic.co/>

¹⁴ <https://neo4j.com/>

Figure 7: Recommendation System

The extracted text relationship is also stored in Linked Data Database (Virtuoso¹⁵). A Virtuoso RDF end point is made available for technical users.

Search and Build Query (Realtime)

This module/extension builds an ElasticSearch query when a user types a question. The query build uses the ranking mechanism to identify the important parts of a query and gives a higher rank if any match is found. Also, it compares user query text relationships to the available text relationships and ranks them accordingly.

There is also a configuration file to add or change current ranking systems and further analysers/filters can be added or removed. This way the behaviour of the search functionality can be easily adapted depending on the harvested data.

Figure 8 represents the workflow of the component - search query builder.

Figure 8: Return the most relevant information

Figure 9, below, represents the dialog framework components and how the response is sent to the given query.

¹⁵ <https://virtuoso.openlinksw.com/>

**Public Service Kweery
Dialogue Framework
Architecture**

Figure 9: Kweery chatbot Dialog Framework Architecture

Multilingual Functionality

Currently Kweery chatbot supports five languages: English, Spanish, French, German and Italian. However, it can be made to handle most languages, depending on the translation engine used. At the moment the system uses the Google translation engine¹⁶. The translation API is part of the NLP extension and can easily be adapted to use any translation API.

¹⁶ <https://cloud.google.com/translate/docs/resources>

To switch to other languages, data should be harvested in those languages (knowledge base) and the language needs to be added to the list of supported languages in the configuration file.

Steps:

- Convert the multilingual query from the source language to English
- Process the information in English
- Extract relevant information in English and translate to the required language

Figure 10, below, represents the multilingual system, which is responsible for translating from one language to another (supported English and Spanish).

Figure 10: Translation process

The Language Mapper module maps the extracted relevant information to the knowledge base in the respective language.

Phase II addressed all the limitations from Phase I. Now the application is multilingual, scalable, conversational and has a substantially better quality of response.

Limitations

- 1 The quality of response is significantly improved with respect to Phase 1. However, with additional text cleaning and information extracting capabilities, quality can be further increased.
- 2 There is a need to account for the translation error (i.e., not all the statements are converted accurately). These errors have an impact on the information extraction step and will need to be addressed.
- 3 The application is not yet production ready and cannot handle multiple users at the moment.

2.3.3 Phase III

In this phase Derilinx concentrated on making the application production ready and improving the quality of response. The limitations of the previous phase were also addressed.

The pipeline in Phase III includes a more extensive text cleaning process with domain-specific words as well as a synonym filter, which was added to the search index. In addition, this phase involved a careful experimentation with the indexing step and with the text meaning extraction phase. Figures 11, 12 and 13 document the JSON code for the Elasticsearch Analysers, the Index filters and Search index schema used in Phase III.

Figure 11 represents the Elasticsearch analyser configuration file and can be modified according to specific needs.

```
analysis:
{
  analyzer:
  {
    pattern_analyzer:
    {
      filter:
      [
        "stemmer",
        "lowercase"
      ],
      pattern: "\\W+",
      flag: "CASE_INSENSITIVE",
      type: "pattern",
      stopwords: "_english_"
    },
    standard_stemming_lowercase_strip_html:
    {
      filter:
      [
        "stemmer",
        "lowercase",
        "synonym"
      ],
      char_filter:
      [
        "html_strip"
      ],
      type: "standard",
      stopwords: "_english_",
      tokenizer: "letter"
    },
    remove_stopwords:
    {
      type: "stop",
      char_filter:
      [
        "html_strip"
      ],
      stopwords: "_english_"
    },
    domain_analyzer:
    {
      filter:
      [
        "stemmer",
        "lowercase",
        "synonym"
      ]
    }
  }
}
```

```

    },
    type: "standard",
    stopwords: "_english_"
  },
  country_tag_analyzer:
  {
    filter:
    [
      "lowercase"
    ],
    char_filter:
    [
      "html_strip"
    ],
    type: "standard",
    stopwords: "_none_"
  },
  standard_stemming_lowercase:
  {
    filter:
    [
      "stemmer",
      "lowercase"
    ],
    type: "standard",
    stopwords: "_english_",
    tokenizer: "letter"
  },
  standard_stemming_lowercase_shingle:
  {
    filter:
    [
      "stemmer",
      "lowercase",
      "synonym",
      "my_shingle_filter"
    ],
    char_filter:
    [
      "html_strip"
    ],
    type: "standard",
    stopwords: "_english_",
    tokenizer: "letter"
  }
}

```

Figure 11: Elasticsearch Analysers for Phase III

Index Filters:

Figure 12 represents the Elasticsearch filter configuration file, where any new filter can be added easily.

```

filters:
  {
    my_shingle_filter:
    {
      max_shingle_size: "5",
      min_shingle_size: "2",
      output_unigrams: "false",
      type: "shingle"
    },
    synonym:
    {

```

```

    type: "synonym",
    synonyms_path: "dlxbot/synonyms.txt"
  }
},

```

Figure 12: Index Filters (Phase III)

Search Index Schema:

The below Figure 13 represents ElasticSearch mapping and data type of the knowledge base (corpus), from where information is extracted for the given query.

```

mappings:
{
  properties:
  {
    c_id:
    {
      type: "keyword"
    },
    country_tag:
    {
      type: "keyword"
    },
    document_id:
    {
      type: "keyword"
    },
    domain:
    {
      type: "text",
      analyzer: "domain_analyzer"
    },
    elastic_search_id:
    {
      type: "long"
    },
    extras:
    {
      type: "object",
      dynamic: "true"
    },
    features:
    {
      type: "nested",
      dynamic: "false",
      properties:
      {
        full_text:
        {
          type: "text",
          analyzer: "standard_stemming_lowercase_shingle"
        },
        named_entities:
        {
          type: "text",
          analyzer: "pattern_analyzer"
        },
        np:
        {
          type: "text",
          analyzer: "standard_stemming_lowercase_shingle"
        },
        text_relationship:

```

```

    {
      type: "text",
      analyzer: "standard_stemming_lowercase_shingle"
    },
    text_relationship_hyper:
    {
      type: "text",
      analyzer: "standard_stemming_lowercase_shingle"
    },
    text_relationship_hypo:
    {
      type: "text",
      analyzer: "standard_stemming_lowercase_shingle"
    },
    text_relationship_syn:
    {
      type: "text",
      analyzer: "standard_stemming_lowercase_shingle"
    }
  },
  p_id:
  {
    type: "keyword"
  },
  sub_domain:
  {
    type: "text",
    analyzer: "domain_analyzer"
  },
  tags:
  {
    type: "text",
    analyzer: "standard_stemming_lowercase"
  }
}

```

Figure 13: Search index schema (Phase III)

In addition to the above search configuration, several other technologies and approaches to further narrow down the extracted related information were explored, namely, cosine similarity, semantic text similarity and sentence transformers.

Testing and bug fixing

In this phase most of the critical bugs have been fixed. However, the software is not completely bug free.

2.3.4 Phase IV (Integration of University of Bielefeld Question generation software)

At this stage an opportunity was identified to integrate some of the “Question generation” functionality developed by the University of Bielefeld (UNIBI) into the pilot. This gave Derilinx the opportunity to improve the accuracy of the chatbot’s answers and UNIBI a chance to test their software in a real-life situation.

Generally, the way this question generation software works is by taking a body of information and then generating a set of questions that can be answered from it. Derilinx supplied the body of

information, in this case the Irish citizens' information website, in the form of a SPARQL endpoint. This was then used to generate a set of questions, which are in turn used to provide an auto-fill function on the chatbot. As the user starts to type in their question, the software displays the list of potential questions from the list generated from the linked list.

For example, the user types in "waste disposal" and is presented with several options related to waste and/or disposal (figure 14).

Figure 14: Question generation

In this way, only those questions within the scope of the data will be processed by the chatbot. This vastly improves its the accuracy, where *accuracy* is defined as:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$$

where TP = True Positive, TN = True Negative, FP = False Positive, FN = False Negative.

If False Positives are interpreted as cases in which the chatbot returned a (poorly matched) answer, as a result of the question not being within scope, setting the FP value to zero improves the accuracy of the answers returned.

Although the user is now restricted to only asking questions allowed by the autofill, their experience is much more positive, as they no longer receive poorly matched answers to questions that are, unknown to the user, outside the chatbot's scope.

Technical details

As the information is stored in RDF, the goal is to generate all possible questions from the RDF triples. The generated question is presented to the user with an autocomplete feature. In the case of a paragraph of information, the nearest question is presented.

```

<http%3A%2F%2Fwww.citizensinformation.ie%2F%23cash-income-not-take-into-account_650f7ec0-9f99-4831-81d9-0aca3d09f376> <http%3A%2F%2Fwww.citizensinformation.ie%2F%23hasPeriod> "104 per year" .

<http://www.citizensinformation.ie/cash-income-not-take-into-account_650f7ec0-9f99-4831-81d9-0aca3d09f376#hasSection> <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#Property> .

<http%3A%2F%2Fwww.citizensinformation.ie%2F%23cash-income-not-take-into-account_650f7ec0-9f99-4831-81d9-0aca3d09f376> <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>
<http%3A%2F%2Fwww.citizensinformation.ie%2F%23Income>.

<http%3A%2F%2Fwww.citizensinformation.ie%2F%23cash-income-not-include-in-the-mean-test_3b2da7ad-530e-476b-b797-184d24bfd37c> <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>
<http%3A%2F%2Fwww.citizensinformation.ie%2F%23Income>.

<http%3A%2F%2Fwww.citizensinformation.ie%2F%23cash-income-not-take-into-account_650f7ec0-9f99-4831-81d9-0aca3d09f376> <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#label> "Cash income not taken into account." .

<http%3A%2F%2Fwww.citizensinformation.ie%2F%23cash-income-not-include-in-the-mean-test_3b2da7ad-530e-476b-b797-184d24bfd37c> <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#label> "Cash income not included in the means test." .

```

Figure 15: Examples of the RDF triples

Figure 16 gives three sample questions, generated from the RDF triples.

```

Proto Question:
What is the time period of the (X|NP)? What was the time period of the (X|NP)?
the time period of (X|NP)?
Is (Y|NP) the time period of (X|NP)?
Q:What is the time period of the cash income not taken into account?
SELECT ?label WHERE {
<http%3A%2F%2Fwww.citizensinformation.ie%2F%23cash-income-not-take-into-account_650f7ec0-9f99-4831-81d9-0aca3d09f376> <http%3A%2F%2Fwww.citizensinformation.ie%2F%23hasPeriod> ?object.
    ?object rdfs:label ?label
    FILTER (langMatches( lang(?label), "en" ) )"
};
A: 104 per year
Q:What is the time period of the cash income not included in the means test?
Q: What was the time period of the HSE Allowances?
...

```

Figure 16: Sample generated questions

2.4 Application Benchmarks

Methodology

- Test the chatbot on the citizensinformation.ie corpus
- Evaluate the sub-pilot for the quality of its results against the search function available on the website (Google-based)
- Consider a consistent set of questions (including some out-of-scope)
- Measure the accuracy of the search function on the website (manually assessed based on knowledge of the corpus)

The chatbot was tested using the citizensinformation.ie¹⁷ corpus. This includes information on a wide range of topics, including COVID-19, Health, Social Welfare, Employment. The site provides a search function which is Google based. This function returns a prioritised list (in order of relevance) of matching links to articles in the corpus.

A set of questions covering all the topics on citizensinformation.ie were generated; these were used for all testing throughout the projects, varying only as described below.

A score was recorded for each question for the site search function; this was the percentage of the time that the most relevant answer (as identified manually through browsing the citizensinformation.ie corpus) was returned at the top of the list. It was interesting to note that this search accuracy improved significantly over the course of the testing.

Notes on Phase I: The chatbot scope only covered the “Moving Country” section of the Irish citizens’ information website so the accuracy figures are based on that limited scope. Phase II was tested twice, the first time with the same 26 questions to provide a comparison to Phase I, then against the full scope (41 questions). All later phases included the whole of the Irish citizens’ information website (16 topics).

Notes on Phase IV: As the chatbot no longer allowed free text questions, some of the questions could no longer be asked (any that were out of scope). To provide a comparison with the previous version a Phase III comparison set – labelled as “Phase III in-scope only” – was generated.

A list of the questions and answers is provided in Appendix 1.

¹⁷ <https://www.citizensinformation.ie/en/>

Phase	Model	Top answer is expected answer	Answer is correct or in suggestions	Score for search function on website	Comments
Phase 1	TF-IDF (Scikit-learn)	35.6%	55.8%	61.5%	Tested using 26 questions covering a single section of the Irish citizens' information website
Phase 2	Elasticsearch Analysers and Boosting with Cosine similarity	35.6%	58.7%	65.4%	Tested using the same 26 questions
		35.4%	62.8%	76.8%	Over 41 questions covering all topics
Phase 2+	BERT Semantic text similarity ¹⁸	46.3%	63.4%	76.8%	Over the 41 questions
Phase 3	Sentence transformer (distilbert-base-nli-mean-tokens) ¹⁹	35.4%	60.4%	76.8%	Over the 41 questions
Phase 3 (in-scope only)	Sentence transformer (distilbert-base-nli-mean-tokens)	38.2%	62.5%	84.2%	Reduced questions to match phase 4 question set (38 questions)
Phase 4	Question generation	55.3%	62.5%	84.2%	Tested over same 38 questions as Phase 3 (in-scope only)

Figure 17: Comparative test results for models for Kweery chatbot

¹⁸ <https://github.com/AndriyMulyar/semantic-text-similarity>

¹⁹ <https://github.com/AndriyMulyar/semantic-text-similarity>

Conclusions from Phase III results

The model implementing BERT Semantic text similarity stood out, with significantly better results than the others for identifying the expected answer as the top answer. This model also returned similar results to the Google search used on the website, once the suggestions were taken into account. This model was used as a basis for the next phase.

Conclusions from Phase IV results

As can be seen in the results above, using the question generation software significantly improved the accuracy of the chatbot's answers, even after the "out of scope" questions were removed from analysis of the Phase III results. This improvement is due to the fact that offering the user options relevant to their search terms immediately makes the results more relevant. The reason that the score is not 100% is that not all search terms from the original questions were represented in the questions offered, and hence it was not always possible to access the "correct" question. However, if the question was modified based on the options offered, the score for the top answer was much higher (82.9%), approaching that of the Google search.

2.4.1 KPI Contributions

This pilot was intended to contribute to the following project KPIs:

Nr	KPI		Benchmarks
4.2	Average reduction in the time (man hours) to convert a resource to linked data at end of project.	90%	Generating linked data from the Irish Citizens' Information corpus for use in Question generation software
4.4	Satisfaction level of early adopters of pilots in a survey	4-5/5	Chatbot pilot user satisfaction survey

Figure 18: Applicable project KPIs

The conversion of the Irish Citizens' Information corpus will be used as a typical user flow by Goethe Universität Frankfurt (GUF), who will generate a benchmark for this task. GUF plans to replicate the workflow used in generating the RDF as a real world example of the use of FINTAN and TEANGA, products of Work Package 3 (WP3) of Prêt-à-LLOD. This will provide an easier and quicker method of generating the linked data resource.

The user satisfaction levels will be measured in a survey once the application is incorporated into the Irish National Open Data portal, later in 2022.

2.5 Future plans

The next steps for Kweery chatbot include:

- Build on the interest expressed by clients in the functionality demonstrated
- Expand the multilingual functionality to other European languages (as requested by interested customers)

- Incorporate the functionality into the Irish National Open Data portal

Derilinx will continue to work with UNIBI to refine the question generation functionality and so improve the accuracy and usability of the chatbot. They will also work with GUF to incorporate the FINTAN and TEANGA flow in the generation of the RDF for any new corpus.

3 Pilot III.B Open Data Dashboard

3.1 Motivation

Open Data provide useful information to users and is readily accessible to the more technical users who may be reading the data programmatically using an API or by other means. We identified a need to improve access to Open Data for less technical users. Open Data is generally formatted as comma-delimited files (CSV), which are machine-readable and can be opened in a program such as Excel or an alternative such as Google Sheets. To access open data information of interest, the user generally has to perform the following:

- Identify the dataset of interest
- Identify the associated resource of interest
- Download the resource
- Open the resource in the spreadsheet software of choice
- Search for the information required

This is a cumbersome and tedious process, in particular for users who are less technically minded, making it difficult to find a single piece of information.

The overall goal of Pilot III.B was to allow users to input a conversational question which can then be converted into a query which would:

1. Identify the dataset/resource containing relevant information
2. Select the relevant information from a CSV file, including searching the data content
3. Return the information

This concept has been extended to geolocated data, such as geoJSON or KML²⁰ files. In this case the information is returned as a map with the ability to search for data within the map.

3.2 Use cases

Three main use cases for the dashboard were identified:

²⁰ [KML Tutorial](#) | [Keyhole Markup Language](#) | [Google Developers](#)

1. To answer simple user questions from information contained in Open Data CSV files
2. To apply a question to multiple files
3. To provide the capability to combine questions using Boolean functions (e.g. searching for a non-Catholic school in Donegal)

Use Case 1

In the first use case, the user simply asks a question and the dashboard returns all the relevant datasets, allowing the user to select one or two datasets to further inspect their resources. Selecting a resource, the user can explore the resource's content and apply automatically generated filters based on the user's original question.

Use Case 2

The second use case requires the user to select two files to apply the same filter to both of them and compare results side by side.

Use Case 3

The third and final use case requires the user to input new custom filters to filter resource's contents.

3.2.1 Data Sources

- Ireland's Open Data Portal²¹
- Dublinlinked: Open Data for the Dublin Region²²
- NLTK corpora, taggers, tokenizers²³

3.2.2 Languages of Interest

For this pilot, the set of languages was extended to include English, Spanish, French, German and Italian.

3.3 Technical Approach

Kweery Dashboard is implemented using a fairly common web application stack:

- Docker²⁴ for containerization
- Flask²⁵ for the API functionalities
- Angular²⁶ for the web application framework
- NLTK²⁷ (Natural Language Toolkit) for NLP.

The application stack has been developed over five phases.

²¹ <https://data.gov.ie/>

²² <https://data.smartdublin.ie/>

²³ http://www.nltk.org/nltk_data/

²⁴ <https://www.docker.com/>

²⁵ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/>

²⁶ <https://angular.io/>

²⁷ <https://www.nltk.org/>

3.3.1 Phase 1

Phase 1 covered the basic infrastructure design and key functionalities:

- Fetching data from datAdore
- Displaying the tabular data in the dashboard
- Including a basic filtering function

Figure 19: Basic design of Kweery dashboard

Text processing:

- Extraction of text entities using NLTK library.
- Extraction of verbs and nouns to create the filters.

Query creator:

- Multiple combinations of entities from n to 1 length, ensuring all possible related datasets from the data source are fetched. This process works by creating a query with all the entities extracted. If there are no results found, the system will combine all the entities in groups of length of entities – 1, perform the search query, and, in case there is no results found, it will keep forming groups of smaller length until all the entities are exhausted.
- Dataset filtering and ordering, based on user input query similarity.

Resource processing:

- Present query data based on automatically created filters (text entities extracted in the text processing step).

The infrastructure of the project is divided into an API backend made in Flask, an Angular dashboard and Docker for containerization.

The workflow:

- The user loads the dashboard and inputs a question

- The dashboard extracts the texts entities and creates multiple data requests to the source server
- The dashboard weights and orders the results, and displays them to the user
- the user selects one or two of the dataset results, and the associated resources are displayed
- The user selects a resource
- The resource's contents are shown, and the user can filter the data

Once the basic functionality of the dashboard was working, we focused on extending its capabilities through the following phases.

3.3.2 Phase 2

Phase 2 extended the NLP capabilities by identifying combination keywords ('and', 'or' and 'not') to expand the functionality of the filtering function.

Apart from detecting verbs and nouns, the NLP step was extended to detect 'and', 'or' and 'not' keywords and attach them to the relevant noun or verb, creating new filters. These filters can be used the same way as in phase 1. In this phase we added the ability for the user to add new custom filters, giving the user full control over the filtering function.

Example workflow in Phase 2:

In response to the query "What is the children's outpatient waiting list for cardiology?", the user is offered and can select the following two datasets: Outpatient and Inpatient waiting list by Group Hospital.

The screenshot shows a dashboard interface with a red sidebar on the left labeled 'Dashboard'. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column is titled 'OP WAITING LIST BY GROUP HOSPITAL' and the right column is titled 'IPDC WAITING LIST BY GROUP HOSPITAL'. Both columns contain introductory text about the National Treatment Purchase Fund (NTPF) and its role in collecting and validating waiting lists. Below the text are two tables. The left table is titled 'Click a resource below to view data' and the right table is titled 'Right Click a dataset to add it for comparison'. Both tables have columns for Name, Description, Format, and Source. The left table lists resources for OP Waiting List by Group Hospital from 2014 to 2020. The right table lists resources for IPDC Waiting List by Group Hospital from 2014 to 2020. At the bottom of the dashboard, there are filter buttons for 'children', 'outpatient', 'waiting list', and 'cardiology', along with a 'Custom filter...' input field.

Figure 20: Response to inpatient and outpatient query

The dashboard lists the various data associated resources for each dataset, and the user can select the most recent data (2020).

The dashboard automatically generates filters that the user can select, based on the user’s query, in this case, “children”, “outpatient”, “waiting list” and “cardiology”:

Figure 21: Preview of data

The user can then select and combine the filters to apply and drill down to the information required. In this case, they create a filter “children and cardiology” and apply it to both resources. The dashboard displays then children’s cardiology information from the inpatients’ and outpatients’ files.

Figure 22: Adding and applying filters

3.3.3 Phase 3

Phase 3 integrated the Kweery Chatbot and Dashboard, allowing the Chatbot to show open data suggestions related to the chat conversation.

To create seamless integration between the Chatbot and the Dashboard two new API endpoints in the dashboard were created:

- Search endpoint: this endpoint allows the chatbot to ask the dashboard whether there are open data datasets relevant to the user question and provides a direct link to the dashboard where relevant.
- Show endpoint: hitting this URL will load the dashboard with the user question and the relevant resources already loaded.

3.3.4 Phase 4

In order to extend the dashboard features, the goal is to allow for its integration with as much open data as possible. The most numerous open data resources are in tabular format (comma delimited files that the dashboard can process). The second most numerous resources are geospatial data in geoJSON, KML and other geospatial formats.

In Phase 4 the dashboard successfully supports geospatial data (geoJSON and KML), displaying it in a map and allowing the user to interact with the data directly in the map. The map can aggregate multiple layers into one and show extra data on every feature.

The map allows to filter the data displayed by using similar filtering functionality than the tabular data (eliminating the natural language processing of the tabular data filtering), thus allowing to drill down the displayed data.

The library used to display the map is Mapbox GL JS²⁸.

Figure 23: Display of geolocated data

²⁸ <https://www.mapbox.com/mapbox-gljs>

The application runs against the European Open Data portal, thus providing access to all Open Data published in Europe.

3.3.5 Phase 5

We extended the dashboard to include a multilingual functionality.

The user can select the language (English, German, Spanish, French and Italian) in which the query will be written and the results will be displayed. This includes the title and description at the dataset level, name and description at the resource level, and the contents (headers) of the data.

Whenever possible the dashboard will use the already provided translations available in the original source metadata. If there is none for the selected language, the metadata will be translated into the requested target language.

The dashboard runs against the European Open Data portal, allowing the dashboard to be used for open data from all European countries.

3.4 Application Benchmarks

The sub-pilot was evaluated for the quality and speed of its results against a manual process. The time and quality benchmarks were set by a user with a translation tool, measuring the time taken to identify and retrieve relevant data. The datasets identified by the application were marked for comparative relevance and the time taken to identify and retrieve.

The criteria for evaluation were the following:

1. Were all the datasets manually identified as relevant identified by the application?
2. How relevant were any additional datasets that were retrieved using the application?
3. Was the data presented to the user in a meaningful form?
4. What was the time saving in delivering meaningful results with the application vs. the manual process?

The analysis has both quantitative and qualitative components.

3.4.1 Testing of Phase 3 (data from data.gov.ie)

User testing with trial users incorporating criteria 1, 2 and 3 above.

Test case 1:

User question: "What is the children's outpatient waiting list for cardiology?"

Dashboard fetched the following datasets:

1. OP²⁹ Waiting List By Group Hospital ³⁰

²⁹ Outpatient

³⁰ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/op-waiting-list-by-group-hospital>

2. IPDC³¹ Waiting List By Group Hospital ³²

Entering the same query on Ireland's Open Data Portal fetched the following datasets:

1. OP Waiting List By Group Hospital
2. IPDC Waiting List By Group Hospital
3. IPDC GI Endoscopy by Group Hospital ³³

Test case 2:

User question: "Are there any non-Catholic schools in Donegal?"

Dashboard fetched the following datasets:

1. Schools³⁴
2. Primary Schools³⁵
3. School Enrolment 2008 – 2011³⁶
4. Data on Individual Schools³⁷
5. Secondary School Locations³⁸
6. Primary School Locations ³⁹
7. Post Primary Schools ⁴⁰
8. EDA70 - Pupils Enrolled in Second Level Schools (Number) by Sex, Type of School, School Programme and Year ⁴¹
9. EDA49 - National Schools and Pupils by Teacher Size of School by Teacher Size of School, Year and Statistic ⁴²
10. Cork (Rochelle Schools) Rainfall Data⁴³
11. Co. Donegal Municipal Districts ⁴⁴
12. Donegal (Dist.Hosp.) Rainfall Data ⁴⁵
13. Donegal Prompt Payment Return Q4 2017 ⁴⁶
14. Donegal Prompt Payment Return Q2 2017 ⁴⁷
15. Donegal Prompt Payment Return Q1 2017 ⁴⁸
16. Donegal (W.W.) Rainfall Data ⁴⁹

³¹ Inpatient

³² <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/ipdc-waiting-list-by-group-hospital>

³³ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/ipdc-gi-endoscopy-by-group-hospital>

³⁴ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/schools1>

³⁵ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/primary-schools>

³⁶ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/school-enrollment-20082011>

³⁷ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/data-on-individual-schools>

³⁸ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/secondary-school-locations>

³⁹ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/primary-school-locations>

⁴⁰ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/post-primary-schools>

⁴¹ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/pupils-enrolled-in-second-level-schools-number-by-sex-type-of-school-school-programme-and-year>

⁴² <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/national-schools-and-pupils-by-teacher-size-of-school-by-teacher-size-of-school-year-and-statistic>

⁴³ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/cork-rochelle-schools-rainfall-data>

⁴⁴ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/co-donegal-municipal-districts>

⁴⁵ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/donegal-disthosp-rainfall-data>

⁴⁶ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/donegal-prompt-payment-return-q4-2017>

⁴⁷ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/donegal-prompt-payment-return-q2-2017>

⁴⁸ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/donegal-prompt-payment-return-q1-2017>

⁴⁹ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/donegal-cullionboy-ww-rainfall-data>

17. CD154 - Donegal Population by Private Households, Occupied and Vacancy Rate by Townlands, and Statistic⁵⁰
18. Revenue Net Receipts by County ⁵¹
19. Tellus Airborne Geophysics - Total Count ⁵²
20. Tellus Airborne Geophysics - Magnetic Intensity ⁵³

Entering the same query on Ireland’s National Open Data Portal fetched 24 datasets:

Figure 24: Top datasets returned from “Are there any non-Catholic schools in Donegal?” query

Test case 3

User question: “National parks to bring my kids to”

Kweery dashboard fetched the following datasets:

⁵⁰ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/gal-population-by-private-households-occupied-and-vacancy-rate-by-townlands-censusyear-and-statistic>

⁵¹ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/revenue-net-receipts-by-county>

⁵² <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/tellus-airborne-geophysics-total-count>

⁵³ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/tellus-airborne-geophysics-magnetic-intensity>

1. National Parks⁵⁴
2. National Parks - Points of Interest ⁵⁵
3. National Parks & Wildlife Service Estuaries⁵⁶
4. National Parks & Wildlife Service Sandbanks⁵⁷

Entering the same query on Ireland's Open Data Portal fetched the following datasets:

1. Irish Semi-natural Grassland Survey 2007-2012⁵⁸

The results of these tests are collated in Figure 25 below.

⁵⁴ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/national-parks>

⁵⁵ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/national-parks-points-of-interest>

⁵⁶ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/national-parks-and-wildlife-service-estuaries>

⁵⁷ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/national-parks-and-wildlife-service-sandbanks>

⁵⁸ <https://data.gov.ie/dataset/irish-semi-natural-grassland-survey-2007-2012>

Test Case 1		“What is the children’s outpatient waiting list for cardiology?”		
	Using Kweery Dashboard		Using the same query on data.gov.ie	
		Percentage of identified datasets directly relevant to query		Percentage of identified datasets directly relevant to query
Were all the datasets manually identified as relevant, found by the application?	Yes	100%	Yes	66%
How relevant were any additional datasets that were retrieved using the application?	n/a, both datasets retrieved were used		Marginal	
Was the data presented to the user in a meaningful form?	Yes, the user could apply the filters suggested to drill down to the relevant data		User could preview the data and perform a basic search	
Question 2		“Are there any non-Catholic schools in Donegal?”		
	Using Kweery Dashboard		Using the same query on data.gov.ie	
		Percentage of identified datasets directly relevant to query		Percentage of identified datasets directly relevant to query
Were all the datasets manually identified as relevant, identified by the application?	Yes	100%	No	0% - no school, Catholic or Donegal-related datasets were returned
How relevant were any additional datasets that were retrieved using the application?	Datasets were counted as relevant if related to schools, Catholic or Donegal	90%		0% - 24 irrelevant datasets returned
Was the data presented to the user in a meaningful form?	The most relevant data was at the top of the list. The user could apply filters to			n/a

	retrieve that information required			
Question 3	"National parks to bring my kids to"			
	Using Kweery Dashboard		Using the same query on data.gov.ie	
		Percentage of identified datasets directly relevant to query		Percentage of identified datasets directly relevant to query
Were all the datasets manually identified as relevant, identified by the application?	Yes	100%	None of the relevant datasets were retrieved	0%
How relevant were any additional datasets that were retrieved using the application?	Datasets were counted as relevant if related to National parks	100%	n/a	0%
Was the data presented to the user in a meaningful form?	The user could apply filters to retrieve that information required		n/a	

Figure 25: Test results for Kweery dashboard

Conclusions from Phase 3 Testing

Results of Phase 3 Testing indicate that the dashboard search function is significantly more accurate than the standard search function available on the Irish National Open Data portal for natural language queries.

3.4.2 Testing of Phase 4 (European Open Data Portal)

The original test criteria were the following:

1. Were all the datasets manually identified as relevant identified by the application?
2. How relevant were any additional datasets that were retrieved using the application?
3. Was the data presented to the user in a meaningful form?
4. What was the time saving in delivering meaningful results with the application vs. the manual process?

As the application uses the European Open Data portal API and displays the first nine results, the data identified manually by accessing the portal user interface and the datasets retrieved by the application will always be identical and so criteria 1 and 2 are no longer relevant. For this reason, the tests for this phase focused on criteria 3 and 4 and the results were compared against performing similar tasks using the European Open Data portal. The test cases included filtering and translation.

Test A: Displaying resources and filtering

To test criterion 3, data in geolocated formats (geoJSON and/or KML) was included. In this case, the data was presented on a map, as it was on the portal, however in the application, the user could further filter the data, which was not possible on the portal.

Test A	Average Time (seconds)	
	Using Dashboard	Using Open Data portal
Complete the search	25	1
Load the resources	50	1
Display CSV resource	14	12 ⁵⁹
Filter CSV resource	1	22 ⁶⁰
Display geoJSON resource	1	1
Filter geoJSON resource	1	98 ⁶¹
Total for CSV	90	36
Total for geoJSON	77	101

Figure 26: Comparison of time to access resources using Dashboard or Open Data Portal + Excel and GIS⁶²

⁵⁹ This includes the time to download then open the CSV file.

⁶⁰ This includes the time to download, open and apply filters to the file.

⁶¹ This includes downloading the file, opening it with a GIS, applying filters to the data.

⁶² Geographic information system such as QGIS

Test B: Viewing resources in translation

For this test, two sets of data were identified; one where the publisher had attached a translation of the data's title and description, and the other where this information was not supplied.

Datasets on the portal which originate from the Irish National Open Data portal are generally not supplied with these translations. When a dataset originating from this portal is viewed in the application in French, the description and all the data headers are translated:

Filters: **esb** **+**

ue	TLIST(Q1)	Trimestre	C02196V02652	Région	C03451V04162	Type de connexion	UNITÉ	VALEUR
ions	20111	2011Q1	IE11	Border	1	New dwelling completion	Number	299
ions	20111	2011Q1	IE11	Border	2	Unfinished	Number	37
ions	20111	2011Q1	IE11	Border	3	Reconnection	Number	40
ions	20111	2011Q1	IE11	Border	4	Non-Dwelling	Number	36
ions	20111	2011Q1	IE12	Midland	1	New dwelling completion	Number	106
ions	20111	2011Q1	IE12	Midland	2	Unfinished	Number	15
ions	20111	2011Q1	IE12	Midland	3	Reconnection	Number	17
ions	20111	2011Q1	IE12	Midland	4	Non-Dwelling	Number	10
ions	20111	2011Q1	IE13	West	1	New dwelling completion	Number	201
ions	20111	2011Q1	IE13	West	2	Unfinished	Number	34

Figure 27: Viewing a dataset originating from the Irish National Open Data portal in French

Accessing this data in translation via the portal involves two steps:

1. Downloading the dataset
2. Translating the data headers into French

The time for translating and then transcribing the translation back into the downloaded dataset depends on how many column headers need to be translated. For a simple dataset, this may be only four, while for more complicated data this number usually increases.

Test B	Average Time (seconds)	Average Time (seconds)	Average Time (seconds)
	Using Dashboard	Using Open Data portal (title/description) already translated	Using Open Data portal (title/description) to be translated
Complete the search	25	1	1
Load the resources	50	1	1
Display CSV resource	14	102 ⁶³	137 ⁶⁴
Total	89	104	139

Figure 28: Comparison of time to view CSV resources in translation

Conclusions from Phase 4

The results of Test A indicate that, although the dashboard is slower at loading the data than the portal, this is offset if the user wants to perform any filtering of the data, in particular of a geoJSON or KML file, where it is faster than the manual process. As the manual process requires specialist software and some technical skills, this is not available to all users. In contrast, the main advantage of using the dashboard is that it does not require technical skills or specialist software to filter a CSV file or geoJSON, and that the whole process is completed within the one application.

The results of Test B indicate a time saving in viewing the data in translation over the manual process.

A further general observation is that the dashboard is currently running on the Derilinx test system and more computing resources would allow to improve its running performance.

3.4.3 KPI Contributions

Nr	KPI		Benchmarks
4.4	Satisfaction level of early adopters of pilots in a survey	4-5/5	Survey of users

Figure 29: Applicable project KPIs

A survey will be developed to collect feedback from users of the application to measure these performance indicators once the functionality is incorporated into the Irish National Open Data portal.

⁶³ This includes the time to download then open the CSV file and translate the column headers.

⁶⁴ This includes the time for translation of the title and description, in addition to the column headers.

3.5 Future plans

The next steps for the dashboard include incorporating its functionality into the Irish National Open Data portal.

It was also noted during the project that not all data published on the European Open Data Portal is machine readable – that is, the host of the data does not accept machine requests as they have a “cross origin request block” in place. This would need to be pursued with the data publishers to have this constrain lifted to provide full functionality on the European Open Data.

4 Conclusions

The goal of this pilot was to deliver a Public Service Query Tool providing the following functionality:

1. Answer multilingual queries on Government and Health Services via a Chatbot
2. Explore Open Data via a dashboard

The chatbot functionality has been demonstrated and the method can be applied to any corpus to generate questions and supply answers. The pilot has not yet been surveyed by users, but this will be done once it is applied to the incorporated into the Irish National Open Data Portal.

The dashboard functionality makes Open Data more useful to the general user as it:

- displays the data in a more accessible manner
- allows the user a more powerful filter of the data in the interface
- provides translations down to the column header level for all datasets

A side effect of this improved accessibility is that any deficiencies in the associated metadata are clearly seen. In this way the functionality can help drive the improvement in metadata content, and so improve the quality of Open Data, an important measurement of Open Data Maturity, which is reflected in the European Open Data report⁶⁵.

The interest expressed in the pilot functionality by the Irish Department of Public Expenditure and Reform will result in the chatbot and dashboard functionality being refined, optimised and incorporated into the Irish National Open Data Portal. This is included in their plan for the portal for 2022.

Derilinx intend to explore whether the European Open Data portal may be interested in the dashboard enhanced search and display functionality.

⁶⁵ https://data.europa.eu/sites/default/files/landscaping_insight_report_n7_2021.pdf

Appendices

Appendix 1 : questions for chatbot

Ref	Scope	Question	Modified Question (Phase 4 selection)
1	Moving country	Do I need a visa to move to Ireland?	Visa required
2	Moving country	What do I need to do to import my car into Ireland?	Importing a vehicle
3	Moving country	Do you have advice for someone returning to Ireland?	returning to Ireland
4	Moving country	If I am Irish, does my spouse have the right to live and work in Ireland?	Right to work
5	Moving country	Can you tell me about the education system in Ireland?	Education system
6	Moving country	I want my 12 year old child to come and live with me in Ireland. What do I need to do?	returning to Ireland with children
7	Moving country	I'd like to study in Ireland. What do I need to know?	studying in Ireland
8	Moving country	I am a refugee from Syria. What are my rights?	convention refugee
8.1		refugee rights	
9	Moving country	How do I apply for refugee status in Ireland?	permission to remain
9.1		How do I apply for asylum in Ireland?	Coming to Ireland as an asylum seeker or refugee.
10	Moving country	I am an Irish citizen. What rights do I have in the UK?	rights in UK
11	Moving country	As an Irish citizen living in Britain, how will Brexit affect my rights?	Brexit rights
13	Moving country	I am going on holiday to Germany, do I need to take out travel insurance?	travel insurance
13.1	Moving country	European health insurance	The European Health Insurance Card.
13.2	Moving country	Health insurance in Ireland	Do you have to buy private health insurance in Ireland
14	Moving country	I am from New Zealand and I'd like to become an Irish citizen. How do I do this?	Who can become an Irish citizen through the Foreign Births Register?.
15	Moving country	I am moving to Ireland, can I bring my dog?	bring pets
17	COVID-19	Do I need to wear a face mask?	wear a face covering
20	Health	Can I get my epilepsy drugs for free	drugs payment scheme
23	Social Welfare	what is the Irish social welfare system	social welfare
25	Social Welfare	how does the means test for social assistance work	the means test
33	Returning to Ireland	How can I retire to Ireland	retiring to Ireland as a returning Irish emigrant

40	Education and training	returning to education	returning to education or training
47	Travel and recreation	drivers with a disability	disabled drivers
55	Consumer	utility companies in Ireland	Utilities: electricity, gas, water.
30	Money and Tax	what protection is there for consumers in Ireland	consumer protection
27	Employment	what should be on my pay slip	pay slips
37	Housing	social housing	social housing
49	Environment	What do I do with my household waste in Ireland	household waste disposal
56	Death and Bereavement	what to do when someone dies	registering a death
60	Family and Relationships	having a baby	birth of your baby